

ENHANCING CREATIVITY IN TERTIARY INSTITUTION THROUGH HOME ECONOMICS EDUCATION FOR EDUCATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The focus of this work is concern with enhancing creativity in tertiary institution through Home Economics Education for Educational Sustainability in south-south Nigeria. The study was a descriptive survey of 2016 respondents from six tertiary institutions in the south-south. The sample comprises 206 respondents representing 10% of the estimated population of student in the chosen tertiary institution. A validated instrument entitled Enhancing Creativity in Home Economics Education for Educational Sustainability Questionnaire (ECHEESQ), validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument ranges from .78 to .85 respectively and the analysis was done with descriptive and inferential statistics. It reviewed ways of sustainable development in home economics education and hindrance encountered by Home Economists in reaching their goals in sustainable development. The findings revealed that home Economic education if properly planned can create jobs opportunities for the teeming unemployed graduate who can foster economic sustainability. Also, it proffered possible strategies of enhancing creativity in Home Economics for sustainable development. This paper submits that enhancing sustainable development is part of the goals of home economics and creativity enhances sustainable development in home economics.

Keywords: enhancing creativity, home economics education, educational sustainability, South-South Nigeria

1. Introduction

Home Economics education has to do with proper management and utilization of family resources in order to meet the needs of all members of the family. According to Anyankoha and Eluwa (2009) Home Economics draws knowledge from many

disciplines such as biological, physical and social science, humanities and arts. The teaching of Home Economics has been of much concern to researchers in recent times. This could be due to the present standard of education in general. Home economics is a subject that deals with the aspect of education for living. This is because it centers on every aspect of human life such as, home, family, community and the nation at large. It is the area of study that provides the prerequisite skills and knowledge to human beings so as to help assist them to be able to attain a more self-reliant and fulfilled life (Ode, 2013). Home economics is a dynamic field of study which central focus is hinged on the improvement of the lives of everyone in the society. The course is self-reliance oriented (Ogbene, 2008). It is a vocational subject aimed at helping people develop desirable social attitude and skills necessary for the world of work, as well as resourcefulness and ability to develop hygiene in all aspect of our lives. Home economics can also be seen as the study of human and material forces affecting homes and families, and the utilization of the knowledge for the benefit of mankind.

Creativity has to do with the ability for an individual to be innovative which is seen in the ability of the individual to create symbols of experience. According to Franklen (2004) creativity is not all about the ability to innovate but in an individual is not only judged by the number of alternatives the individual can generate but also by the uniqueness of those alternatives. Fundamentally one who is creative exhibits such qualities as flexibility, tolerance of ambiguity or unpredictability, and the enjoyment of things hereto for unknown. Creativity in home economics is the fundamental premises and genesis of entrepreneurial activity. Creativity is not an exclusive right Enhancing creativity in home economics education for sustainable development possession of a chosen few. It is in all human beings at varying degrees. However, training has been found to manifest creative abilities. Home economics inculcates in the individual creative skills (Anyankoha *et al*, 2009). Creativity is an important characteristic of an entrepreneur. It is the capacity of persons to produce idea of any sort, which is essentially new or previously unknown to the producer (Ogbene, 2006).

To be creative, one must first decide to generate new ideas, analyze the ideas and sell the ideas to others. In other words, a person may have synthetic, analytical or practical skills but may not be able to apply the skills to problem solving that potentially involve creativity (Ode, 2013). Creativity involves a complex process, research suggests that environmental conditions promote or suppress creativity. It has been identified that some environmental influences are essential for creative ideas. For example, an individual seeking or pursuing inspiration must feel a sense of freedom. The atmosphere must be conducive for exploration and some form of positive reinforcement in support of creative efforts must be forthcoming (Molokwu, 2010) Creativity can be enhanced in the students by giving creative tasks which will call for creative production and opportunity to experiment without strict evaluation (Molokwu, 2010). The exchange of information, resources and new ideas enhance and challenge creativity in home economics and in turn leads to sustainable development.

Sustainable Development According to Nigerian environmental study action team FGN (2015) sustainable development seeks to meet the needs and aspirations of

the present, without compromising the ability to meet those of the future generation. It is the process through which the explanation of resources, the direction of investment, the orientation of technological developments and institutional changes are in harmony and enhance both current and the future potentials to meet human needs and aspiration (Okpetu & Nwankwo, 2002). Sustainable development can be defined as the economy, which depends on the stock of natural capital, human capital and technology which the future generation inherits from the present generation (Okpetu, 2002). The goal of sustainable development is lasting improvement in the quality of life and not just short term improvements that disappear rapidly at the end of the project cycle. Thus, sustainable development is all about improving the quality of life without compromising the needs of the future generation. Sustainable development is development that lasts. It is a concept that is very relevant to home economics (Okpetu, 2002). The link between home economics and sustainable development is manifested in their ability to combine changing domestic responsibilities and obligations with sustainable development. Home economics generally engages in self-employment as part of a household production system. This in turn, improves economic independence, personal fulfillment and a better understanding of one self. According to Okpetu (2002), sustainable development is geared towards improvement in the quality of life of the people through the application of practical and scientific skills.

2. Statement of the problem

Home Economics as a vital subject in secondary schools have been a failure due to the fact that the teachers who are expected to give the instructions are of low academic standard with low level of creativity in the subject area. Such teachers cannot teach effectively. This is to say that those who had education in Home Economics perceived themselves better able to maintain a positive outlook than those who did not. Home Economics subjects are particularly able to balance household chores and office work responsibilities than those who did not have education in Home Economics subjects. The problem of this study is: What can creativity enhanced in home economics education for educational sustainability in tertiary institution in south-south Nigeria

2.1 Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to carry out a study on enhancing creativity in tertiary institution through home economics education for educational sustainability in south-south Nigeria. Specifically the study intends to:

1. Examine the influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability.
2. Determine the influence of entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability

2.2 Research questions

In connection with the stated objectives of the study, the following research questions were formulated for the study.

1. To what extent does creativity in home economics education influence educational sustainability?
2. What is the influence of entrepreneurial skills influence educational sustainability in home economics?

2.3 Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study.

1. There is no significant influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability.
2. There is no significant influence of entrepreneurial skills on educational sustainability in home economics.

3. Literature reviewed

3.1 Influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability.

Creativity in home economic has been identified as one of the most distinct of human attributes. It is indeed a special case of problem solving in which originality is emphasized. Onu (2006) conducted a study on the topic creativity in home management and educational sustainability in home economics. The study was ex-post facto design with a sample of 234 respondents drawn from the study area. A 35 items questionnaire was used to gather data. The study used a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher entitled creativity in home economics education (CHEEQ) and the statistical analysis was executed with chi square and independent t-test and the findings revealed that creativity is the disposition to make and recognise valuable innovations. It manifests itself in the ability of the individual to create his own symbols of experience. The study further revealed that creative if he has the ability to combine or rearrange established patterns of knowledge in a unique fashion.

Onu, (2006) in his own opinion asserts that a creative person sees beyond the veil and brings back light and is able to perceive new relationships and constructions in which independence, spontaneity and originality are fused. Osuala (2012) conducted a study on the influence of creativity on educational sustainability in home economics. The study was a descriptive survey with a sample of 128 respondents drawn from the study area. a ten items questionnaire was used to gather data, the statistical analysis was executed with independent t-test and the findings revealed that the processes of bringing together creative and innovative ideas and combining them with management and organizational skills in order to combine people, money and resources to meet an identified need and thereby, create educational sustenance. From the foregoing, it is not enough; therefore, to conceive a business idea. What makes the differences is the ability

to be creative with ideas and develop something new and out of the ordinary. There is hardly any business idea that has not been conceived by entrepreneurs.

3.2 Influence of entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability

Entrepreneurship education according to Onu (2006) is the type of education which provides learners with the basic knowledge, skills, attitude, and ideas for self-reliance. In other words, entrepreneurship education through the inculcation of entrepreneurial skills should make recipients proficient in career related areas and so launch them into the business world with a view to overcoming the problem of unemployment and over-dependency on white-collar jobs. (Franklen (2004) labels home economics education as the people's profession because it is a multidiscipline functional delivery system. Tupac (2008) conducted a study on the topic influence of entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability. The study adopted the correlational design with a sample of 201 respondents drawn from the study area. A 32 items questionnaire was used to gather data. The study used a standardized instrument titled entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability (ESHEES) and the statistical analysis was executed with one way ANOVA and independent t-test and the findings revealed that home economics education is a means through which the individual may be led to a stronger growth and development in entrepreneurial skill development, thus enabling him to take responsibilities in the family and society. In the definitions of home economics above, functionality is emphasized. This implies the ability of knowledge and skills gained to help individuals who has acquired them to be able to relate to real life situations and solve their needs.

Home economics education can be seen, therefore, as the solution to the many problems facing individuals, families, communities in Nigeria particularly in the areas of skill acquisition, inter-personal family relationship, healthy living, resource management, poverty reduction and job creation. In Nigeria, time and trends have evolved over the years with regards to what functional and creative education should be. With the competitive global business world and the emergence of knowledge economy the challenge for home economics education is, therefore, to prepare graduates who can connect the body of knowledge, the practice of home economics and the contemporary competitive global market.

In line with the spirit of entrepreneurship, Nwabuona, (2005) was interested in finding out the influence of entrepreneurial skills and educational sustainability in home management. The study adopted the experimental design (2x2 design) with a sample population of 347 respondents drawn from the study area. A 29 items questionnaire was used to gather data. The study used a standardized instrument titled entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability (EESHMQ) finding revealed that the establishment of entrepreneurship centers in the universities and other higher institutions of learning so as to enhance entrepreneurship education. These centres are to be funded by the education tax fund and students are expected to channel the knowledge and energies acquired at devising creative strategies

and learning skills to function as entrepreneurs. Home economics education and entrepreneurship are two sides of the same coin. Home economics education is a key player in entrepreneurship development process and so has important role to play in reducing massive graduate unemployment and the social menace which it represents. The question before us is how to address the weakness in the system and reposition home economics education for producing creative entrepreneurs who can survive the competitive business in Nigeria as well as contribute to family and national building.

Home economics education must evolve to be in tune with current global business changes and challenges. Molokwu (2010) re-branding can help home economics stand out and achieve professional goals through renewing what is taught, what methods are used to teach to ensure what is taught is transferable and has value for the new times. Nwabuona (2005) suggests the inclusion of entrepreneurship education content areas such as small scale business, managing business opportunity, global market, business plan, marketing analysis, risk management and record keeping will enhance the functionality of the course to the benefit of the students.

4. Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design with 206 respondents sampled from the study area. Questionnaires were administered to the subjects, who were M.Ed, Ph.D lecturers of Home Economic department in the institutions. These subjects were selected for the study because given the greater time pressure, it was reasonable to hypothesize that educated lecturers would more reasonably apply educational learning experience and strategies to coping behaviour. Descriptive and survey design were employed for the study. Means, percentages and standard deviations were tabulated for interpretations of demographic factors. Inferential statistical analysis were employed in testing the stated null hypotheses with one way ANOVA at 0.05 significance. A 32 items questionnaire was used to collect information which were validated by experts in the study area.

4.1 Presentation of results

The results of the data collected are presented hypothesis-by-hypothesis as shown below.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability.

The independent variable in this study is creativity with three levels (high, moderate and low) while the dependent variable is educational sustainability. To test this hypothesis, one way-ANOVA was employed as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of one Way- ANOVA on the influence of creativity
 in home economics education on educational sustainability

Group	N	X	SD
High	67	16.03	3.01
Moderate	111	14.83	2.86
Low	23	16.48	2.52
Total	201	15.78	2.80

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	Sig.
Between Group	89.47	2	44.73	5.40*	.005
With Groups	1639.43	198	8.28		
Total	1728.90	200			

*p<.05

Results in Table 1 show that with 201 respondents that constituted the analysis of the study 67, were of high level of creativity with mean and standard deviation of 16.03 and 3.01, for moderate level of creativity 111 respondents were found with mean and standard deviation of 14.83 and 2.86 while the remaining 23 were from low level of creativity with mean of 16.48 and standard deviation of 2.56 respectively. With inferential statistical analysis the p-value was found to be .000 which is less than the chosen alpha of .05 thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability. To ascertain the direction of means, a Post-Hoc multiple comparison was calculated with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Post-hoc comparison with Fisher's Least Significance Different (LSD) of the influence
 of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability

Creativity	N	High	Moderate	Low
High	67	16.03	1.20*	-.45
Moderate	111	3.00	14.83	1.65*
Low	23	-.70	4.02	16.48
MSW=8.28				

*<.05, critical t = 1.960, df = 200.

a = Group means are placed along the diagonal

b = Difference between group means are placed above diagonal

c = Fisher LSD are placed below the diagonal

The means comparison with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) in Table 2, revealed that the mean differences for high years and moderate years has a statistical mean difference as (*p<.05; t=3.00; p=.008, X=1.20). For high and low and above there is no significance mean difference as (p>.05; t=-.70; p=.520, X= -.45), while for moderate and low there is a statistical mean difference as (*p<.05; t=4.02; p=.013, X= 1.65). This implies that the mean differences lies in high and moderate, moderate and low respectively.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant influence of entrepreneurial skills on educational sustainability in home economics.

The independent variable of this hypothesis is entrepreneurial skills with three categories namely high, moderate and low while the dependent variable is educational sustainability. To test this hypothesis, One-Way ANOVA was employed as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of One-way Analysis of Variance with the influence of entrepreneurial skills on educational sustainability

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	SD
High	102	10.58	3.16
Moderate	31	7.06	3.12
Low	68	12.43	2.39
Total	201	10.02	3.22

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	Sig.
Between Group	1473.77	2	736.89	82.62*	.000
With Groups	2649.01	297	8.92		
Total	4122.79	299			

*p<.05

Results in Table 3 show that with 201 respondents that constituted the analysis of the study 102, were of high level of entrepreneurship skills with mean and standard deviation of 10.8 and 3.16. 31 are from moderate level of entrepreneurship skills with mean and standard deviation of 7.06 and 3.12 while the remaining 68 were from low level of entrepreneurship skills with mean of 12.43 and standard deviation of 2.22 respectively. With inferential statistical analysis the p-value was found to be .000 which is less than the chosen alpha of .05 thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant influence of entrepreneurial skills on educational sustainability in home economics. To ascertain the direction of means, a Post-Hoc multiple comparison was calculated with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) and presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Post-hoc comparison with Fisher's Least Significance Different (LSD) on entrepreneurship skills on educational sustainability

Entrepreneurship skills	N	High	Moderate	Low
High	102	10.58	3.52*	-1.85*
Moderate	130	8.80	7.06	5.36*
Low	68	-3.94	11.91	12.43
MSW=8.92				

*<.05, critical t = 1.960, df = 298.

a = Group means are placed along the diagonal

b = Difference between group means are placed above diagonal

c = Fisher LSD are placed below the diagonal

The means comparison with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) in Table 4, revealed that the mean differences for high and moderate has a statistical mean difference as (* $p < .05$; $t = 8.80$; $P = .000$, $X = 3.52$). For moderate and low level of entrepreneurship skills the mean difference is statistically significance as (* $p < .05$; $t = -3.93$; $p = .000$, $X = -1.85$), while for moderate and low level of entrepreneurship skills there is a statistical mean difference as (* $p < .05$; $t = 11.91$; $p = .000$, $X = 5.36$). This implies that the mean differences lies in high and moderate, high and low and moderate and low level of entrepreneurship skills.

5. Discussions of findings

The finding of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant influence of creativity in home economics education on educational sustainability. Creativity in home economic has been identified as one of the most distinct of human attributes. It is indeed a special case of problem solving in which originality is emphasized. The finding agrees with that of Onu (2006) whose findings revealed that creativity is the disposition to make and recognize valuable innovations. It manifests itself in the ability of the individual to create his own symbols of experience. The study further revealed that creative if he has the ability to combine or rearrange established patterns of knowledge in a unique fashion. The present finding is in agreement with that of Osuala (2012) whose findings revealed that the processes of bringing together creative and innovative ideas and combining them with management and organizational skills in order to combine people, money and resources to meet an identified need and thereby, create educational sustenance. From the foregoing, it is not enough; therefore, to conceive a business idea.

Also hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant influence of entrepreneurial skills in home economics education on educational sustainability, this is in harmony with Tupac (2008) findings revealed that home economics education is a means through which the individual may be led to a stronger growth and development in entrepreneurial skill development, thus enabling him to take responsibilities in the family and society. In the definitions of home economics above, functionality is emphasized. This implies the ability of knowledge and skills gained to help individuals who has acquired them to be able to relate to real life situations and solve their needs. The present finding concur with that of Okpetu (2002) who found that the establishment of entrepreneurship centers in the universities and other higher institutions of learning so as to enhance entrepreneurship education.

6. Conclusion

Creative entrepreneurship can be developed and enhanced through home economics education. In the face of unemployment and unemployable graduates produced every year from our higher institutions of learning, developing creativity in students through entrepreneurship education is a way forward. Home Economics is a great tool for

enhancing creativity and sustainable development. It has successfully created a way forward by making its graduates to develop skills that will help them to be independent and self-reliant thereby reducing the rate of unemployment.

7. Recommendations

1. Home economics teachers should make effort to improve their creativity in the area of entrepreneurship education since it is a new concept in home economics. This can be done through private studies, seminars, workshops and other relevant activities.
2. Teachers should encourage creativity and originality in the students by encouraging practical exploration and use of experimental method of teaching Enhancing creativity in home economics education for sustainable development.

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